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Undergraduates Academic Research Skills

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Undergraduates research skills course

Overall course setting:

The course settings are presented according to Brinker and Schumacher (2014).

- Study regulations and conditions:

The academic research course is an obligatory course for all undergraduate students in all majors and faculties and it is a prerequisite for doing a graduation project.

Students who are to be enrolled in this obligatory credited course are supposed to have completed an advanced English course.

- Examination regulations and rules:

Students are supposed to sit for a quiz in the first quarter of the course, a mid-exam half way through the course, and a final exam after the end of the course. In addition, towards the end of the course and during its procession, students are supposed to submit three assignments as a form of mini assessments for the research skills they acquired during the course along with an oral assessment in the form of an interview about the contents of their assignments. The passing mark for this course is 50 marks out of 100.

- Infrastructure:

The course has a blended nature with one session with a traditional setting based on face to face weekly meetings. The class meets once a week for a session of 90 minutes. The class is usually equipped with a computer, a projector and speakers. Some sessions are held in a computer lab with enough internet connected computers for all students. Other sessions are held at the university central library for educational purposes. The other weekly scheduled session takes place online with a duration of 90 minutes, the sessions depend on Google meet software.

- Module-Handbook:

A student friendly text book is being used for this course. The term student friendly is suggestive of the nature of the layout of the book as it has simplified format and easy access to different sections and parts.

Analysis of the target group: (students)

Students who are enrolled in this course belong to different faculties and majors (Business, Dentistry, Pharmacy, Architecture, Engineering and Law). Most of them are in their senior academic year. Each taught group of consist of 25 students. Those students do not have any prior knowledge of practicing academic research including the APA

guiding rules which are the core of the current course. Most of the students are used to be teacher-dependent learners in most of their courses. However, there are some distinguished students that can be considered as independent learners that seek information voluntarily. All of the students are Syrian Arabs; However, there are several groups of students which come from different Syrian governorates. But, the majority of the students comes from Damascus, Damascus countryside, and Assuwayda'a governorate.

Teacher's competences

The course instructor is well informed of academic research practices and has published several academic researches and contributed to some academic books whether as a whole or with chapters. The instructor has been teaching this course for five years and has introduced several modifications and improvements including authoring a new and revised curriculum and text book for the course. The instructor also exhibits good social and personal skills when it comes to dealing with students. The instructor is keen on providing support, assistance, answers and feedback to students in a manner that matches the students condition and abilities. The instructor encourages students to use their cognitive abilities including critical thinking in addition to allowing students to learn through experimenting and creating personalized perspectives of things and topics.

Teaching content

The core content of the course depends basically on the APA manual. In addition, several resources were consulted to included suitable exercises and examples on quotations, summaries, paraphrases, in-text citations, combining resources and referencing. The reason for adopting the APA rules as the core content of the course is because They are the most common set of rules used in academic research and have been continuously revised over the years. The course follows the smooth transition of the course book that gradually guide students through the writing an academic research paper starting with topic selection with in an area of interest, inquiring, taking a stance through a thesis statement, using academic search engines, judging references, getting familiarized with a paper's format and layout according to APA, data collection methods, data analysis, results presentation, summarizing, paraphrasing, quoting, citing and referencing. It is worth noting that each of the learned skill has been allocated a suitable amount of time for explanation, examples, and practice along with a matching assessment embedded in the required assignments.

A detailed lesson plan

Timing & phase	Learning outcomes and teaching aims	Content and terminology	Media and material	Didactic method and tasks	Evaluation method and tasks
Introductory: 15 min	Getting acquainted with academic search engines	Using the engine's search box and filtering the results to the most recent and most relevant/ terminology: search, choose, select	An internet wired computer lab	Asking students to go to google scholar home page, write a key word related to their topic, browse the results sheets, check the resources dates	Visual examination of students input and out-put on their computers' screens.
Elaborative phase: 30 min	Finding useful information that answers the research questions written in a previous session	Read, skim	Pdf or printed Articles	Asking students to read the abstract, scan the main headings of the article and skim its sections.	Asking questions and checking selected articles.
Progressive phase: 25 min	Taking notes of important points	Highlight, underline, write	Articles, note book	Asking students to underline or highlight the main points, write down key phrases.	Checking students' notes
Final phase: 20 min	Writing a paragraph using the previous notes	Write, complete, finish, check	Students' notes	Asking students to use their notes to write full grammatical sentences expressing	Checking students' writing

				the main points in the original text	
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Educational objectives

According to the taxonomy of educational objectives by Bloom et al (1956), this course presents the students with the opportunity to demonstrate higher order outcomes as they will be able to do the following by the end of the course.

Students will be able to define a topic for research, describe, discuss and explain its aspects and importance. In addition, they should demonstrate the topic's implications and examine its effects or consequences. Furthermore, they will be able to contrast and compare their topic to other topics (tools, methods) in order to highlight its importance. Eventually, students will be able to suggest a workable combination of solutions for specific issues along with a justification and defense of their argument.

Learning Outcomes

1-Each of the learning outcomes of this course is measurable commencing with an action that students can demonstrate e.g. finding a research topic and constructing a personal argument.

2- Each of the outcomes is distinct focusing on one action e.g. search, find, write, ask, quote, summarize.

3- Each of the outcomes is pitched at an appropriate level e.g. guided steps of searching for a reference (using an academic search engine, writing in a key word, selecting the best reference).

Following the guidelines of constructive alignment and Biggs and Tang (2009), Biggs (2014), and HEA (2012), Students who successfully complete this course will be able to :

1- Select research topics.

2- State their argument or thesis.

3- Inquire about the topic with personalized arguments.

4- Apply APA rules and understand search mechanisms.

5- Be familiar with academic search engines and electronic libraries.

6- Judge and select suitable references.

7- Avoid unintended plagiarism like copying without changing the structure or without citing the source correctly.

8- Use quotations, summaries, paraphrases correctly.

9- Make a list of references.

10- Realize the importance of voicing their opinion and views through their written discussion and arguments which makes their work significant distinguished.

11- Believe in the contribution they can add to society by doing research no matter how small, they can still shed light on some neglected issues.

12- Believe in the importance of research practices as part of their academic life.

13- Be interested in venturing in search quests for not tackled issues in their surroundings or society and thus set out to find solutions and argue for their effectiveness.

The course motivational design:

The course fulfills Keller's suggested model of motivational design (2009) as it captures students' attention by intriguing them with the exploration process of the online libraries or the physical libraries and the richness of their sources that are one click away. In addition, the course fulfills the students' needs by guiding them in the topic selection process by selecting topics that are relevant to their majors and matches their interests. Furthermore, the course helps the students believe that their selected topics are important and do make a difference and add to the body of knowledge and contributes to society's well fair. Finally, the course gives the students a sense of satisfaction added via the instructor's compliments, constructive criticism and advice.

Bibliography

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